

DEPENDENCE OF LIVE WEIGHT ON CONSTITUTION TYPES IN BLACK KARAKUL SHEEP UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF THE USTYURT PLATEAU

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Abstract. This article examines the main biological indicators of black Karakul sheep under the conditions of the Ustyurt Plateau, focusing on live weight and absolute growth. Differences according to constitution types have been identified, and conclusions are presented.

Keywords: Ustyurt Plateau, black, Karakul sheep, live weight, absolute growth, constitution types.

Introduction. The study of growth and development indicators of Karakul sheep plays an essential role in improving their productivity through the efficient use of these characteristics [19, p.154].

The growth and development features of Karakul sheep are determined by specific natural patterns. In this process, heredity and constitution type have significant importance. Moreover, many researchers emphasize that environmental factors also greatly influence the manifestation of productivity indicators and the full utilization of this potential.

Monitoring the growth and development of Karakul sheep is of great importance for increasing their productivity [49, pp.48–51; 50, pp.29–30].

Live weight is a crucial trait that primarily determines the health, productivity, and constitutional robustness of Karakul sheep. However, it is a variable trait influenced by seasonal changes, pasture productivity, and the physiological condition of the animals. Based on these considerations, maintaining a stable level of fatness in Karakul sheep is important for achieving high productivity.

In our experimental work, we determined the live weight of Karakul lambs based on their constitution type. The obtained data are summarized in table 1.

Table 1.

Live Weight

Constitution Type	Number of Heads	Live Weight of Lambs at Different Ages (kg)		
		At Birth	At Weaning	At 12 Months
		X±Sx		
Coarse	25	3.82±0.12*	26.01±0.52*	38.78±0.77
Robust	25	3.49±0.08*	25.78±0.79	37.08±0.59
Fine	25	3.11±0.05	24.82±0.63*	35.19±0.67

*p < 0.05

The data in table 1 show that at birth, lambs of the coarse type had a live weight of 3.82±0.12 kg, while those of the robust type weighed 3.49±0.08 kg, and fine-type lambs weighed 3.11±0.05 kg (p < 0.05). This tendency continued at later ages: at weaning, the live weights were 26.01 kg, 25.78 kg, and 24.82 kg respectively. At 12 months, these values were 38.78 kg, 37.08 kg, and 35.19 kg (p < 0.05).

In conclusion, live weight differences were observed according to age dynamics. At birth, coarse-type lambs were superior by 8.7% compared to robust types and by 8.6% compared to fine types.

Live weight indicators determine the growth and development between age stages and are expressed through absolute growth figures. Table 2 presents the data on absolute and daily growth obtained from our experiments.

Table 2.

Absolute and Daily Growth Indicators

Lamb Age Period	Indicator	Constitution Type		
		Coarse (n=25)	Robust (n=25)	Fine (n=25)
		X±Sx		
From birth to weaning	Absolute growth (kg)	22.19±0.9*	22.30±1.5*	21.71±1.8
	Daily growth (g)	147.9±11.4*	148.6±12.1	144.7±11.8*
From weaning to 12 months	Absolute growth (kg)	12.77±0.8*	11.3±0.4	10.4±0.4*

Lamb Age Period	Indicator	Constitution Type		
		Coarse (n=25)	Robust (n=25)	Fine (n=25)
		X±Sx		
	Daily growth (g)	70.9±3.1**	62.8±1.9**	57.8±1.6

*p < 0.05, ** p < 0.001

Conclusion. Accordingly, daily growth indicators between birth and weaning were 147.9±11.4 g, 148.6±12.1 g, and 144.7±11.8 g for the coarse, robust, and fine types, respectively.

During the period from weaning to 12 months, absolute growth was 12.77±0.8 kg in coarse-type lambs, 11.3±0.4 kg in robust types, and 10.4±0.4 kg in fine types. Corresponding daily growth values were 70.9±3.1 g, 62.8±1.9 g, and 57.8±1.6 g, respectively (p < 0.001).

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